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PHYTOCHEMICAL AND PROXIMATE ANALYSIS OF SELECTED MEDICINAL PLANTS

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ABSTRACT

The phytochemical investigation is effective in discovering bioactive markers of plants for their therapeutic value. Hence several phytochemical surveys have been carried out for detecting diverse groups of naturally occurring phytochemicals. Identifying different classes of phytoconstituents present in various parts plants and extracting the active components could be further taken for investigation and research. Present study describes some quality control parameters like extractive values, preliminary phytochemical studies, ash value, foreign organic matter, foaming index, swelling index, loss on drying and crude fibre of selected plants namely *Pterospermum suberifolium*, *Givotia moluccana*, *Ixora parviflora*. All methods were carried out using standard methods. For extractive values and preliminary studies various solvents like hexane, chloroform, ethyl acetate, acetone, methanol, ethanol and water were used. Three plants showed more extractive value and significant phytoconstituents like alkaloids, flavonoids, glycosides, saponins, phenols, terpenoids, and tannins in methanolic extract. There was no foreign organic matter in all three plants. The foaming index was less than 100 for *P.suberifolium*, *G.molucanna* and greater than 1000 for *I.parviflora*. The total ash value was obtained as 12.36%, 11.58%, 11.78%, the swelling index was 7.4cm, 6.2cm, 3.6cm, LOD was 11%, 4.68%, 9% and crude fibre content was 26.58%, 14.18%, 41.24% for *P.suberifolium*, *G.molucanna* and *I.parviflora* respectively. The plants resulted in identification of major secondary metabolites by which various pharmacological activities can be established. Other proximate values gave the quality control aspects of plants that are helpful for standardization.

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INTRODUCTION

Plants have been used for medicinal purposes long before prehistoric period. Natural products, which have evolved over millions of years, have a unique chemical diversity, which results in diversity in their biological activities and drug-like properties. Those products have become one of the most important resources for developing new lead compounds and scaffolds.^[1] Natural products will undergo continual use toward meeting the urgent need to develop effective drugs, and they will play a leading role in the discovery of drugs for treating human diseases, especially critical diseases. Traditional medicine is the oldest form of health care in the world and is used in the prevention, and treatment of physical and mental illnesses.^[2] Different societies historically developed various useful healing methods to combat a variety of health and life-threatening diseases. TM is also variously known as complementary and alternative, or ethnic medicine, and it still plays a key role in many countries today.^[3] There is great potential for future discoveries from plants and other natural products which, thus, offer huge potential in deriving useful information about novel chemical structures and their new types of action related to new drug development.^[4]

Traditional systems of medicine continue to be widely practiced on many accounts. Population rise, inadequate supply of drugs, prohibitive cost of treatments, side effects of several synthetic drugs and development of resistance to currently used drugs for infectious diseases have led to increased emphasis on the use of plant materials as a source of medicines for a wide variety of human ailments.^[5] Recently, WHO (World Health Organization) estimated that 80 percent of people worldwide rely on herbal medicines for some aspect of their primary health care needs. According to WHO, around 21,000 plant species have the potential for being used as medicinal plants.^[6]

Herbal medicinal products are the ones which are obtained from the plant resources for the treatment and wellbeing of mankind. It is very much essential that even the quality of the herbal medicines is being controlled as that of the chemically synthesized medicines. But unfortunately the regulation norms for the herbals are not as strict when compared to the synthetic drugs. This is leading to a decrease in the quality standards of the herbal products by intentional and sometimes unintentional adulteration, spurious drugs, substitution of drugs, and many other ways which are prone to decreasing the quality of the herbal materials which are marketed and consumed for the healthy survival. But instead of this, it is leading to hazardous effects on the health of the consumers. So it is very much required to control the quality standards of the herbal drugs and products for the betterment of the mankind. In this aspect there has been a possible practice of adulteration to meet the market demands or to earn the profits. Adulteration, substitution, and lack of skilled personnel are the main reasons for unavailability of genuine herbal drugs. By use of advanced quality control techniques and suitable standards, there is need to assure the quality of the medicinal herbal products.^[7]

The plants were selected based on the literature that they were traditionally well known. *Pterospermum suberifolium* leaf paste is applied to treat fracture and inflammation^[8] it also has antioxidant property^[9]. *Givotia moluccana* used in treatment of rheumatism, skin diseases, dandruff and wound healing^[10]. *Ixora parviflora* aerial parts were used as antioxidative, antibacterial, gastroprotective, hepatoprotective, antidiarrhoeal, antinociceptive, antimutagenic, antineoplastic and some metabolic disorders^[11]. The importance of quality control and standardization of botanical products is of utmost concern for global acceptability of these drugs in the modern system of medicine^[12]. In this article an attempt was made to establish quality control parameters of selected plants for the standardization process.

Pterospermum suberifolium

Givotia moluccana

Ixora parviflora

MATERIALS AND METHODS

Plant collection and processing

The fresh leaves of *Pterospermum suberifolium*(Ps), *Givotia moluccana*(Gm), *Ixora parviflora*(Ip) were collected from Manuguru forest, Telangana by Ravi.G, Taxonomist and authenticated. The leaves were washed under running tap water and cleaned. The leaves were air dried at room temperature for 15 days as plants have to be dried immediately as soon as the collection or may lead to spoilage of plant materials^[13]. The dried leaves were ground into a fine powder using mixer grinder.

Extractive values

Solvents used were in increasing polarity like Hexane, Chloroform, Ethyl Acetate, Acetone, Methanol, Ethanol and Water. Extractive values are primarily useful for the determination of exhausted or adulterated drugs. The extractive value of the crude drug determines the quality as well as purity of the drug. [14] The leaves powder of 5g was macerated with each of 100ml of Hexane, Chloroform, Ethyl Acetate, Acetone, Methanol, Ethanol and Water separately in a closed conical flask for 24 hours (Fig1), frequently shaking for first 6 hours and stand for 18 hours. Filtered and 25ml of filtrate was evaporated to dryness, dried at 105°C and weighed (Fig2). Calculated the percentage of extractive value with reference to the air dried sample (as % w/w).

Fig 1: Extracts collected into china dish after 24hr maceration (a) Ps, (b) Gm, (c) Ip.

Preliminary phytochemical studies

Phytochemical screening was performed to identify various phytochemicals in Hexane, Chloroform, Ethyl Acetate, Acetone, Methanol, Ethanol and Water extracts of the three plants used in the study, the phytochemicals were identified by color tests using standard methods. [15,16]

Development of standard analytical parameters

Physical parameters like ash value, foreign organic matter, foaming index, swelling index, loss on drying and crude fibre were performed according to standard official methods. [17,18]

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Extractive values (%w/w)

All the three samples showed different yield of extract in different solvent. We could find mostly that as the polarity increases the soluble capacity of the solvent increases. All the results of the solvent extractive values in % w/w were tabulated in table 1 and the dried extracts were presented in the fig 2. For all the three plants methanol showed high extractive yield compared to other solvents. So the methanolic extracts were used for further study.

Fig 2: Dried extracts with various solvents (a) Ps, (b) Gm, (c) Ip

Table 1: Extractive values of leaves of three plants with various solvents.

S.NO	SOLVENT	<i>P.suberifolium</i>	<i>G.molucanna</i>	<i>I.parviflora</i>
1	n-hexane	4.8% w/w	7.2% w/w	2.4% w/w
2	Chloroform	6.4% w/w	11.2% w/w	4% w/w
3	Ethyl acetate	3.2% w/w	12.8% w/w	3.2% w/w
4	Acetone	5.6% w/w	16% w/w	4% w/w
5	Methanol	14.4% w/w	19.2% w/w	20% w/w
6	Ethanol	12.8% w/w	18.4% w/w	20% w/w
7	Water	14.3% w/w	18.8% w/w	16% w/w

Preliminary Phytochemical Evaluation of Extracts

The tests showed the presence of major secondary metabolites like Alkaloids, Glycosides, Tannins, Flavonoids, Saponins, Phenols, Steroids, Terpenoids etc and nutritive matter like Proteins and Carbohydrates in three plants. The phytochemical analysis is important to evaluate the possible medicinal utilities of a plant. ^[19] The results of the tests were tabulated in table 2. The presence of the compound is indicated by + (plus) and the absence of compound indicated by - (minus).

Table 2: Preliminary phytochemical evaluation of three plants using various solvent extracts.

Test	Hexane			Chloroform			Ethyl Acetate			Acetone			Methanol			Ethanol			Water		
	P S	G M	I P	P S	G M	I P	P S	G M	I P	P S	G M	I P	P S	G M	I P	P S	G M	I P	P S	G M	I P
Alkaloids																					
Dragendroff's	-	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+
Mayers	-	+	+	-	-	+	-	+	+	-	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	-
Wagners	-	+	+	-	+	+	-	-	+	+	+	-	+	+	+	+	+	+	-	+	+
Glycosides																					
Test A	-	+	+	-	+	+	-	+	+	-	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+
Test B	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	+	+	-	+	+	-	+	+	-	+	+
Tannins																					
FeCl ₃	+	-	+	+	+	+	-	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	-	+	+	+	-
Gelatin	-	-	-	+	-	-	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	-	+	+	-	+	+
Proteins																					
Biuret	-	+	+	-	+	+	-	+	+	-	+	+	-	+	+	-	+	+	-	+	+
Xanthoprotic	-	+	+	+	+	+	-	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+
Amino Acid																					
Millons	+	+	-	+	+	-	+	-	-	-	-	-	+	+	+	-	+	-	+	-	-
Ninhydrin	-	+	+	-	+	+	-	+	+	-	+	+	-	+	+	-	+	+	-	+	+
Carbohydrates																					
Molish	-	+	-	-	+	+	-	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+
Flavonoids																					
Shinoda	-	+	-	+	+	-	+	+	-	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+
Alkaline Reagent test	-	-	-	+	+	-	+	-	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	-	+	+	+
Saponins																					
	-	+	+	-	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	-
Phenols																					
	-	+	+	+	+	-	+	-	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	-	+	+	+
Steroids																					
	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	-	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	-	+	-	-	+	-
Terpenoids																					
	+	+	+	+	+	+	-	+	+	-	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	-	-	-
Gums & Mucilage																					
	+	-	-	-	+	+	+	-	+	-	+	+	-	+	+	-	-	-	-	-	-

+ indicates presence of the compound, - indicates absence of the compound

Proximate Analysis of three plants

Various physical parameters like foreign organic matter, total ash content, loss on drying, crude fibre, swelling index and foaming index showed in different way by the three plants which was tabulated in table 3. From the results it can be noted that there was no organic matter in all the three plants. The total ash was found to be 12.36% in Ps, 11.58% in Gm, 11.78% in Ip. Loss on drying was 11% in Ps, 4.68% in Gm and 9% in Ip. Crude fibre was to be 26.58% in Ps, 14.18% in Gm, 41.24% in Ip. Swelling index was 7.4ml, 6.2ml, 3.6ml in Ps, Gm and Ip respectively. In foaming index the height of the foam is greater than 1 for Ip and less than 1 in Ps and Gm. The figures of Total ash content (Fig 3), Crude fibre (Fig 4), Swelling index (Fig 5), Foaming index (Fig 6, 7, 8) were given.

Fig 3: Total Ash Content of Ps, Gm, Ip.

Fig 4: Crude fibre of Ps, Gm, Ip.

Table: 3 Proximate analysis of the leaf powder of the three plants.

Parameter	PS	GM	IP
FOM	Nil	Nil	Nil
Total Ash	12.36%	11.58%	11.78%
Acid insoluble ash	4.52%	2.45%	5.87%
Water soluble ash	6.42%	4.93%	6.46%
LOD	11%	4.68%	9%
CRUDE FIBRE	26.58%	14.18%	41.24%
SWELLING INDEX	7.4ml	6.2ml	3.6ml
FOAMING INDEX	<100	<100	>1000

Fig 5: Swelling index of Ps, Gm, Ip.

Fig 6: Foaming index of Ps.

Fig 7: Foaming index of Gm.

Fig 8: Foaming index of Ip.

CONCLUSION

The extractive values of the plants showed highest in methanol solvent. The preliminary phytochemical analysis showed the presence of major secondary metabolites like alkaloids, tannins, phenols, terpenoids, flavonoids etc., in the three plants. Thereby these secondary metabolites contribute to various pharmacological activities. The proximate analysis of the leaf powders gave the standards for the plants as a parameter of quality control. This study can be useful for future analysis to determine various possible biological activities.

Recommend Future Research

As it is evident that these plants consist of active phytoconstituents it may be recommended that characterization and isolation of bioactive compounds is needed. Investigation of pharmacological activities for the extracts and isolated compounds plays an important role for the researchers in drug discovery process.

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Conflicts of Interest

There is no conflict of interest.

ABBREVIATION

WHO: World Health Organization

TM : Traditional Medicine

Fig: Figure

PS: *Pterospermum suberifolium*

GM: *Givotia moluccana*

IP: *Ixora parviflora*

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